

Cardiac Disease in Obstetric Practice in a Tertiary Care Centre: A Retrospective Study

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Abstract:

Background: Worldwide, heart diseases are of concern perennially. The field of Obstetrics is also considered as a sensitive field, encompassing the maternal as well as the neonatal well-being. Hence, undoubtedly, Cardiology, Obstetrics, and other medical specialities face a formidable obstacle in the one to three percent of pregnancies that are complicated by heart disease. The increasing incidence shall be attributed to the increasing diagnostic modalities available across the country and easy availability to the public at the primary and the secondary care level. Cardiac disease of pregnancy is a significant cause of or morbidity and mortality and has been cited to be present between 1 to 4% of all pregnancies. Hence a study of prevalence and outcomes of cardiac disease in a prescribed location becomes a mandatory tool in provision of expertise in management of heart disease, thus helping in reducing maternal mortality and morbidity. This study is conducted in Government Medical College Hospital, Karur to obtain a clear picture of epidemiology and outcomes of cardiac disease in pregnancy.

Aims: 1) To study the prevalence of congenital and rheumatic heart disease complicating pregnancy in GMCH Karur. 2) To study the maternal and perinatal outcomes of heart disease in pregnancy. 3) To study the pattern and frequency of occurrence of complications as a result of heart disease.

Settings and Design: This study was carried out in the dept of Obstetrics and Gynecology of Govt. Karur Medical College Hospital in Karur district of Tamilnadu, India, from Jan 2023 to Dec 2023 as a retrospective study.

Materials and Methods: In all patients detailed history – medical history, obstetric history were taken. Vital parameters checked and basic investigations done. Weight of the patient checked. Detailed general examination and obstetric examination done. Gestational age confirmed by USG. All the patients attending OPD, Casualty and Labour ward are included in the study. Screening Echocardiogram was done routinely for all patients in the OPD and inpatient was done. Also, diagnostic Echocardiography was also performed in patients who presented with cardiac symptoms. In addition to the patients diagnosed in the facility, the patients who were referred from primary and secondary care institutions, who had findings in Echocardiography were included in the study. All the pertaining details are maintained in a register, and they were consolidated at the end of study period, and statistical analysis done to arrive at the results.

Results and Conclusion: This study found the prevalence of heart disease in pregnancy to be 4.4 %, which is comparable to Indian standards and various other research studies. Where, the prevalence of rheumatic/ valvular disease is found to be 3.9%, which is as usual and as expected higher than congenital, which is only 0.5%. From this study, it is evident that, the prevalence of heart disease remains the same throughout developing countries. With improvement in early detection and implementation of school health programmes, many school children are screened and underlying heart diseases are corrected, which has caused an increase in prevalence of operated heart diseases in the community, which again are of concern.

Keywords: Heart Disease, Rheumatic, Congenital.

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Introduction

Worldwide, heart diseases are of concern perennially. The field of Obstetrics is also considered as a sensitive field, encompassing the maternal as well as the neonatal well-being. Hence, undoubtedly, Cardiology, Obstetrics, and other medical specialities face a formidable obstacle in the one to three

percent of pregnancies that are complicated by heart disease [1]. Although the prevalence of rheumatic heart disease (RHD) has decreased significantly in industrialized countries, it remains high in low-income regions and is a leading cause of maternal morbidity and mortality. Congenital heart

diseases, in the other hand also contribute a proportion of maternal mortality and morbidity, in addition to RHD.

The increasing incidence shall be attributed to the increasing diagnostic modalities available across the country and easy availability to the public at the primary and the secondary care level. Cardiac disease of pregnancy is a significant cause of morbidity and mortality and has been cited to be present between 1 to 4% of all pregnancies [2]. Although there is extensive explanation about the cardiac diseases in pregnancy available in literature, the maternal and fetal outcomes of cardiac disease shall be rightly altered by timely diagnosis and management.

Preconceptional counselling in turn plays a pivotal role in primordial prevention of complications that arise as consequences of gestation [1,2]. Hence a study of prevalence and outcomes of cardiac disease in a prescribed location becomes a mandatory tool in provision of expertise in management of heart disease, thus helping in reducing maternal mortality and morbidity. This study is conducted in Government Medical College Hospital, Karur to obtain a clear picture of epidemiology and outcomes of cardiac disease in pregnancy.

Aims and Objectives

- To study the prevalence of congenital and rheumatic heart disease complicating pregnancy in GMCH Karur.
- To study the maternal and perinatal outcomes of heart disease in pregnancy.
- To study the pattern and frequency of occurrence of complications as a result of heart disease.

Review of Literature: Several studies have looked at the possibility of estimating mortality and morbidity in pregnant women who suffer from cardiac disease.

Significant usage of the CARPREG scoring system, developed by Siu et al., for assessing pregnancy risk. This score was adequate for diagnosing congenital heart disease, VHD, myocardial disease, and arrhythmias, but it was useless for prosthetic heart valves, aortopathy, and pulmonary artery hypertension (PAH) [1,2].

Silversides et al. developed CARPREG II, an expanded risk score. According to the pathology and severity of cardiac disease, many predictors (previous cardiac episodes or arrhythmias, baseline ejection fraction, and so on) are given a maximum of 3 points and a minimum of 1 point in the CARPREG II score: NYHA Class III/IV, cyanosis, mechanical valve, ventricular dysfunction, high-risk left-sided valve diseases/left ventricular outflow tract blockage, pulmonary arterial hypertension, coronary artery disease, late-pregnancy evaluation, and no

previous cardiac intervention [1]. Justin Paul, et al, stated that, based on recent reports from high-income countries with a low maternal mortality ratio (MMR) of 7–12 per 100 000 live births, 23–27% of maternal deaths are attributable to cardiovascular diseases and cardiomyopathies [1].

Hemapriya, Prathap, et al, in their study in Mysore have stated that the prevalence of heart disease in pregnancy was 1.76%. There were 77 (41.6%) women with congenital heart disease and 72 (38.9%) with rheumatic heart disease. 61.6% of the women were from rural background, and 38.4% were from the urban areas. Isolated mitral stenosis was the most common defect in those with rheumatic heart disease; and atrial septal defect was the most common congenital lesion seen [2].

Materials and Methods

This study was carried out in the dept of Obstetrics and Gynecology of Govt. Karur Medical College Hospital in Karur district of Tamilnadu, India, from Jan 2023 to December 2023 as a retrospective study. In all patients detailed history – medical history, obstetric history were taken.

Vital parameters checked and basic investigations done. Weight of the patient checked. Detailed general examination and obstetric examination done. Gestational age confirmed by USG. All the patients attending OPD, Casualty and Labour ward are included in the study. Screening Echocardiogram was done routinely for all patients in the OPD and inpatient was done. Also, diagnostic Echocardiography was also performed in patients who presented with cardiac symptoms.

In addition to the patients diagnosed in the facility, the patients who were referred from primary and secondary care institutions, who had findings in Echocardiography were included in the study. The patients were allotted identification numbers, and they were periodically followed by a collaboration with the primary health team in the field. Every patient was assigned a follow-up schedule. Follow-up was continued till 6 weeks of delivery, if the patient had delivered. All the pertaining details are maintained in a register, and they were consolidated at the end of study period, and statistical analysis done to arrive at the results.

Inclusion Criteria:

- All antenatal mothers consenting for the study
- All postnatal mothers in puerperal period consenting for the study
- All antenatal/postnatal mothers having pathological changes in screening/ diagnostic echocardiogram

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patient not giving informed consent
- Patients having physiological findings in echo-

cardiogram.

Statistical Analysis**Table 1: Age Distribution**

Age Group	No. Of Cases	%
<20 Yrs	4	6
21-25 Yrs	32	48
26-30 Yrs	15	23
31-35 Yrs	13	20
>35 Yrs	2	3
Total	66	100

It is found that there is significantly higher number of cases in the age group 21 to 25 years (48%), and the least being 3% cases more than 35 years of age.

Table 2: Socioeconomic status

SES	No. of Cases	%
CLASS I	00	0
CLASS II	08	12
CLASS III	20	30
CLASS IV	29	44
CLASS V	09	14
Total	66	100

The maximum number of cases fall in the class IV SES (44%) according to modified Kuppuswamy scale, while no case was from from class (class I).

Table 3: Urban Vs Rural

Locality	No. of Cases	%
Urban	23	35
Rural	43	65
Total	66	100

There is a statistically significant difference in the number of cases between urban and rural areas, with maximum cases from rural areas (65%).

Table 4: Parity and Deliveries

Parity	Cases	%	Deliveries	%
Primi	42	64	34	62
Multi	24	36	21	38
Total	66	100	55	100

The number of primigravida are significantly higher than that of multigravida in both cases (64%) and deliveries (62%).

Table 5: Timing of Diagnosis

Timing of Diagnosis	No of Cases	%
Previous Pregnancy	12	18
Current Pregnancy	Antenatal	49
	Postnatal	5
Total	66	100

Number of cases identified in present pregnancy (82%) seems to be significantly higher than previous pregnancy (18%), and also, the number of cases diagnosed antenatally (74%) is more than that postnatally.

Table 6: Mode of Diagnosis

Mode	No. of Cases	%
Screening Echo	53	80
Diagnostic Echo	13	20
Total	66	100

53 cases (80%) were diagnosed by screening without any complaints, whereas only 13 cases (20%) were diagnosed with symptoms, which is significantly lower.

Table 7: Lesion wise distribution

Lesion Type	No of Cases	%
Rheumatic Valvular	38	58
Congenital	9	14
Other Valvular	14	20
Operated	5	8
Infective	0	0
Total	66	100

Most of the cases were rheumatic lesions (58%), while only 9 were congenital (14%), showing a statistically significant difference.

Table 8: Split Up of Rheumatic/ Valvular lesions

Lesion	No. of Cases	%
Mild MR	13	25
Moderate MR	8	15
MVP	7	13
Mild TR	9	17
Moderate to severe MS	3	6
Mild AR	3	6
Mod AR	2	4
Mild PAH	4	8
Mod PAH	3	6
TOTAL	52	100

Lesions which form a majority are Mild MR (25%), followed by Mild TR (17%), followed by moderate MR and MVP, where there is no statistical difference.

Table 9: Split up of congenital lesions

Lesion	No. of Cases	%
ASD	6	67
VSD	3	33
Total	9	100

Only two varieties of congenital lesions, both acyanotic, were identified, and the highest incidence being ASD, followed by VSD.

Table 10: Previous Cardiac Surgery

Prev Surgery	No. of Cases
ASD Closure	2
TOF Operated	1
PTMC	1
BMV	1
Total	5

Previously diagnosed and preconceptionally operated heart disease cases were identified in the study.

Table 11: NYHA Classification

NYHA Class	No. of Cases	%
I	58	88
II	4	6
III	4	6
IV	0	0
Total	66	100

There is a significantly higher number of cases in the NYHA class I, amounting to 88%.

Table 12: Onset of Labour

Onset	No of Cases	%
Spontaneous	37	67
Induced	18	33
Total	55	100

Out of the total cases delivered, say 55 cases, 37 patients (67%) either went into spontaneous labour or elective Lscs, while only 18 patients (33%) were induced due to Obstetric indications.

Table 13: Mode of Delivery

Mode	Primi	Multi	Total	%
Normal Vaginal	19	8	27	49
Assisted Vaginal	5	1	6	11
LSCS	10	12	22	40
Total	34	21	55	100

There is a statistically significant difference between vaginal (normal and assisted) and Cesarean deliveries in the study, vaginal deliveries accounting to 60%, and LSCS accounting only to 40%

Table 14: Primary Vs Repeat LSCS

LSCS		No. of Cases	%
Primary	Elective	0	0
	Emergency	10	45
Repeat	Elective	9	41
	Emergency	3	14
Total		22	100

There were no elective primary caesarean sections. There were 10 emergency primary LSCS, with a primary LSCS rate of 45%, while in repeat sections, 9 were elective (41%) and 3 were emergency caesareans (14%).

Table 15: Primary LSCS Indications

Indications	No. of Cases
Fetal Distress	4
Failed Induction	2
BREECH/FPD	1
CPD	3
Total	10

Table 16: Perinatal Outcome and Follow-up

Perinatal Outcome	No. of Cases
Live Birth	55
IUD/Still Birth	0
Term	53
Preterm	2
LBW	3
Heart Disease In NB	1
Nicu Admissions	9
Perinatal Mortality	1

There was 1 perinatal mortality due to extreme preterm/sepsis/respiratory distress, and 1 newborn of heart disease mother had congenital heart disease- ASD on neonatal echo.

Table 17: Complications

Complications	No. of Cases
Failure	3
Pulmonary Edema	2
Infective Endocarditis	0
Arrhythmias	1
Ventilatory Support	4
Cardiac Arrest	1

Table 18: Maternal Outcome

Outcome	No. of Cases
Referral Out	6
Inpatient Monitoring	3
Discharged As ANC	2
Delivered And Discharged	55
Mortality	0
Total	66

There were nil maternal mortality in heart disease mothers, and 55 patients were delivered and discharged, while 3 patients are retained as IP, and 2 were monitored as OP cases. 6 patients were

referred out for Multidisciplinary approach to higher centre.

Discussion

This study found a similar prevalence of heart disease in pregnancy, 4.4 %, as compared to 4.3 % in a study by Salam et al, various other research studies have shown a prevalence between 0.5 to 4.0%, which are in concordance with this study [4]. Where, the prevalence of rheumatic/ valvular disease is found to be 3.9%, which is as usual and as expected higher than congenital, which is only 0.5%. Bangal VB et al, have found that the average age of heart disease in pregnancy is 26.14 with a SD of 4.5 years [5], and in our study, the maximum frequency of heart disease was observed in the age group of 21 to 25 years, which is also in terms with previous study.

This study reveals that 64% were primigravida and 36% were multigravida, which is in contrary to a study by Burlingame et al, where only 44.5% were primigravida and 55.5 were multigravida [6]. Rheumatic heart disease was found to be the most common lesion (78%), followed by congenital heart disease (14%), and followed by operated and corrected heart diseases, which account to only 8% of the total heart diseases. As the majority of patients in developing countries are malnourished, lack sanitation and hygiene, lack access to healthcare. etc., the prevalence of rheumatic heart disease has remained high for years. With improving surgical options, the likelihood of women born with CHD to survive till reproductive age has increased, and now the number of women with CHD/ Corrected CHD are on a higher trend as compared to previous studies [1,3].

The mitral valve was the most affected valve in RHD, accounting to 46%, followed by tricuspid valve, amounting to 17%, which is in a clear concordance with study done by Puri S et al, and many other studies [7]. Five people in this study have undergone cardiac operations, and ASD closure was the maximum surgery, followed by TOF repair in CHD and PTMC and Balloon Mitral Valvotomy for RHD, which matches with the study by Dina Aisha Khan et al and Agarwal et al, There were of 60% vaginal deliveries and 40% LSCS in this study. The incidence of assisted vaginal deliveries were 11%. In this regard, many studies have a similar result, while certain studies like one by Stangl V et al, showed a reduced rate of vaginal deliveries (45.2%), and increased rate of LSCS (54.5%) [8].

Maternal complications, antepartum and intrapartum were encountered, and the commonest was cardiac failure, followed by pulmonary edema, and even one patient had a cardiac arrest. One patient had arrhythmia because of cardiac disease. 4 patients were in ventilatory support because of heart disease, were either weaned or referred to higher centre for a multidisciplinary approach. With adequate manpower and interdisciplinary approach, our centre managed the complications,

and there was nil maternal mortality due to heart disease complicating pregnancy [3].

As far as perinatal complications are considered, preterm babies were 3, low birth weight were 3, and 1 extreme preterm neonate succumbed as a result of sepsis. With follow-up neonatal echo, 1 neonate found to have ASD, interestingly the daughter of the mother with corrected ASD. All were livebirths, and there were no stillbirths or intrauterine deaths. The primary LSCS rate is found to be 45% in mothers with heart disease [3]. In repeat caesarean sections, most were elective CS. All mothers were covered for Family planning. 100 copper T coverage for primiparas and 92% Sterilisation coverage for multiparas were achieved. The rest 8% of multiparas were covered with Copper T devices.

Conclusion

This study found the prevalence of heart disease in pregnancy to be 4.4 %, which is comparable to Indian standards and various other research studies [4]. Where, the prevalence of rheumatic/ valvular disease is found to be 3.9%, which is as usual and as expected higher than congenital, which is only 0.5%. From this study, it is evident that, the prevalence of heart disease remains the same throughout developing countries. With improvement in early detection and implementation of school health programmes, many school children are screened and underlying heart diseases are corrected, which has caused an increase in prevalence OD operated heart diseases in the community, which again are of concern.

1. There is no routine indication of induction in heart disease complicating pregnancy. Similarly, LSCS is not performed in heart disease, unless obstetrically indicated.
2. Even with routine care and monitoring of cardiac disease complicating, intrapartum and postpartum complications can occur any-time. Avoiding fluid overload and being ready for combating complications, ensuring compliance to treatment are key factors in preventing maternal mortality and morbidity.
3. Postpartum monitoring of patients must be strengthened even after discharge from tertiary care center by primary care team and home visits, so as to avoid unnecessary delay in diagnosis postnatally.
4. Peripartum cardiomyopathy can set in the absence of any other organic lesion in any mother, and hence care to be provided for all parturient mothers in a routine basis.

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